

D3.2 Publication of Phase 1 simulations (EERIE)

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Executive Summary

The EERIE project is conducting two main phases of coupled model simulations, Phase 1 and Phase 2, to advance climate modeling efforts. This document summarises the standardisation and publication of the Phase 1 simulations, which are based on CMIP6 HighResMIP and DECK -style experiments carried out by EERIE groups. A detailed user-guide explains how to openly access these refined datasets from their repositories - the Earth System Grid Federation (ESGF) and the Centre for Environmental Data Analysis (CEDA, for Met Office data) archive.

In this initial data release, priority is given to the most requested and currently available regridded variables as described in the [EERIE Data Management Plan \(DMP\)](#). Given the substantial size of the datasets and to enhance usability for end-users, the decision has been made to give preference to Earth System Model (ESM) outputs on a standard regular grid. The publication of lower-priority variables such as variables on native ESM grids and late-available variables will proceed gradually as they become available. This approach ensures timely publication to high-demand data while maintaining a structured publication workflow.

In addition, most of the entire EERIE ESM output (all ICON-ESM-ER, IFS-FESOM2-SR and IFS-AMIP simulations, subsets of IFS-NEMO-EERIE and HadGEM3-GC5E) is made available in the [EERIE intake catalog](#), [DKRZ's STAC catalog](#) and via the Eerie.cloud server directly after production. This is further explained in the DMP.

1. Experiments and Variables

The Phase 1 simulations for EERIE were defined in the Description of Action and further detailed in Deliverable D4.1. Two different simulation designs are being used to provide complementary insights and enable comparative analysis.

1. **HighResMIP-style** coupled model simulations, following the CMIP6 HighResMIP protocol (Haarsma et al.), have been conducted by three EERIE groups: AWI (using IFS-FESOM2), MPI-M (using ICON-ESM-ER), and BSC (using IFS-NEMO). These simulations require relatively short simulation years, starting from initial conditions representative of the 1950s.
2. **CMIP6 DECK-style** coupled model simulations have been carried out by the Met Office. These simulations follow a different approach, requiring a long pre-industrial spin-up using 1850s forcings to reach equilibrium before the main experiment phase.

Together, these two simulation strategies allow for robust comparisons and a broader understanding of model behavior across different experimental setups. The completed simulation years for each run and each model are presented in table 1 and 2.

We aim to publish as many variables as defined in the [Data Request](#) created at the beginning of the project. Given the late and asynchronous availability of raw outputs and the different processing times, datasets are processed and published on a rolling basis (see Table 1 and 2 for completion dates of raw model outputs for each model). Consequently, the publication proceeds in multiple batches.

Publication of output on a regular grid is prioritized because it fulfills the stakeholders requirements as it is interoperable with most community workflows. EERIE decided that all their ESMs should provide regridded data on the same regular $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$ latitude–longitude grid. To achieve this, the raw output undergoes a post-processing regridding step before being finalized for publication. The IFS-NEMO workflow differs from the other EERIE models in that it produces regridded output for most variables. However, vector fields (e.g., ocean velocities) are produced on irregular grids because rotation is

required before interpolation, a step that MultIO (the model output library) cannot perform on the fly. Therefore, all vector fields are written on the native ocean grid, and interpolation to a regular latitude–longitude grid is performed offline.

Model	1950-control (years)	1950-hist (years)	Highres-future-ssp245 (years)
ICON-ESM-ER	100 (Completed on 13 Aug 2025)	65 (1950-2014) (Completed on 7 May 2025)	36 (2015-2050) (Completed on 01 Aug 2025)
IFS-FESOM2	65 (Completed on 02 March 2025)	65 (1950-2014) (Completed on 26 Feb 2025)	36 (2015-2050) (Completed on 26 July 2025)
IFS-NEMO-EERIE	93 (Expected completion on 31 October 2025)	65 (Completed on 28 May 2025)	36 (2015-2050) (Completed on 8 September 2025)

Table 1: Completed Phase 1 HighResMIP simulations.

HadGEM3-GC5E config	PiSpinup (years)	PiControl (years)	historical (1850-2014)	Scenario (2015-2100)
LL (res: 130-100 km)	240	200	1850-2014	2015-2100
MM (res: 60-25 km)			1850-2014	2015-2100
HH (res: 20-8 km)			1850-2014	2015-2070 (ongoing)

Table 2: Completed Phase 1 CMIP6 DECK simulations.

2. Standardization

To ensure data interoperability, reproducibility, and long-term usability (FAIR principles), a central prerequisite for publication is that all EERIE datasets must follow the EERIE data standard. Its definition (2.1.), variable mapping (2.2), implementation (2.3) and quality assurance procedures (2.4) are described in detail in the following sections.

The code bases of the EERIE ESMs, ICON-ESM-ER, IFS-FESOM2-SR, and UM-NEMO-SI3, cannot be easily modified to produce fully standard-compliant files directly. Instead, these models produce ‘raw output’ that deviates from the standard. Section 2.3 describes in detail how this raw output is post-processed using different approaches and tools.

2.1 EERIE Data Standard Definition

The EERIE data standard defines how ESM output needs to be stored and formatted to be suitable for global sharing and analysis of ESM output. It combines requirements for variable shape including dimensions, coordinates and attributes, metadata description as well as technical requirements like the output file format. It has branched from the CF-compliant CMIP data standard defined in [CMIP output requirements](#) and [CMIP6 global attributes](#) and has been extended with EERIE-specific variables, ESMs and experiments.

The EERIE MIP tables, also called CMOR tables, are a machine-readable serialisation of this data standard (in JSON format). These tables are maintained and made available in the [EERIE Data Request Tools](#) repository. As only minor changes have been introduced to the CMIP data standard, no *new* documents were created. Instead, only the EERIE MIP tables were edited and their changes were logged by git.

CMOR tables and their supporting metadata files consist of three types of tables:

1. **CMOR Variable definition tables:** Example: EERIE_Amon.json. Contains a set of variable definitions including e.g. their coordinates and units as requested in the EERIE Data request.

2. **Auxilliary tables:** Example: EERIE_coordinate.json. Defines e.g. coordinates including their values (e.g. requested pressure levels).
3. **Controlled Vocabulary (CV):** EERIE_CV.json. Contains all required or global attributes and their allowed values.

The following kind of additions to the CMIP data standard have been made to match EERIE requirements:

- **New variables:** EERIE specific variables - such as the newly introduced product of x-ward directed sea water velocity and salinity [uso](#) - were added. These are collected in separate MIP tables (named *HR*) to clearly distinguish EERIE requirements from original CMIP6 definitions.
- **Protocol adoption:** The original CMIP6 HighResMIP scenario `highres-future` is defined such that the forcing is aligned to the SSP5-8.5 scenario. Since EERIE chose to run SSP2-4.5 instead of SSP5-8.5 scenario, we added a new entry to the controlled vocabulary (CV) table: `highres-future-ssp245`.
- **Attribute update:** All the EERIE models (e.g. ICON-ESM-ER) were defined in the CV including their source attribute. Datasets produced by these models contain attributes and attribute values as defined in this CV entry.

2.2. Variable Mapping

Variable mapping means to match the correct raw model output variable for a given EERIE data standard variable as defined in the EERIE MIP Tables. This mapping is software-independent as it only allows mathematical recipes for transformation and therefore the first step required for standardization in post-processing. For a full mapping, the input file, name, units and, if necessary, positive direction and recipe of each raw model variable is needed.

With careful scientific validation, we verified each linkage. This includes preserving accuracy and physical meaning. Some mapping examples are listed below

- The positive direction of atmospheric fluxes such as heat flux shortwave, longwave or northward, eastward stress should be corrected to match with the CMOR standard.
- The atmospheric variable [geopotential above surface](#) ($\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-2}$) needs to be divided by Earth's gravitational acceleration ($g=9.80665 \text{ ms}^{-1}$) to get geopotential height (z_g, m).
- Variables like total precipitation, surface runoff, snow depth, snowfall rate and moisture flux need to be scaled by 1000 to account for units change.
- Squared variables such as `tossq`, `zossq` or `siconc` have wrong units in ICON-ESM-ER.

For [ICON](#) and [IFS-FESOM](#), the mapping to EERIE standard variables is kept in external tables, with one row for each standard variable. In contrast, the post-processing tools of the other models store this mapping information internally. As long as the raw output is not changing from one simulation to the next, these tables remain valid and can be reused. E.g., since all ESMs with IFS contribution used the same IFS output configuration, the IFS table of IFS-FESOM can be applied to all IFS simulations.

Proper variable mapping enables downstream tools and data users to recognize, interpret, and compare both raw output and standardized EERIE data seamlessly, promoting interoperability across diverse datasets.

2.3. Implementation

Depending on the ESM, two different standard implementation strategies have been applied: Modifying the ESM code base to enable the model to directly output data in standard format (IFS-NEMO) and post-processing raw model output in a further step (ICON-ESM-ER, IFS-FESOM2-SR, HadGEM3-GC5). Both approaches have advantages: While standardization in post-processing is flexible and modular, model code changes save resources such as storage space. The post-processing scripts were created such that they remain reusable for upcoming phase 2 simulations. They are shared at gitlab repository [EERIE CMOR scripts](#). Each procedure for each model is described separately in the following paragraphs.

For ICON-ESM-ER, IFS-FESOM2-SR, we used a dedicated CDO (Climate Data Operators) operator for standardization, the **CDO CMOR** operator. The **CDO CMOR** operator integrates the CMOR library directly to CDO, providing a streamlined interface for producing CMIP-compliant NetCDF output. The Climate Model Output Rewriter (CMOR) is a main part of this workflow. It is a software library originally designed to help modeling centers to format their data according to the CMIP data standard, but additionally enabling users to flexibly create any standard if defined in MIP tables. CMOR applies the necessary metadata, variable names, units, dimensions, and file structures (including model names, experiments, institutions, and frequency).

What is CDO? CDO is a software tool used to process and analyze large volumes of climate model data. It can perform a wide range of tasks, such as selecting variables, averaging over time, changing the grid resolution, or converting file formats, all from the command line. CDO is widely used because it is fast, flexible, and supports many standard climate data formats like NetCDF and GRIB.

[\(Documentation\)](#)

The CDO CMOR version we have been using and adapted is “*Climate Data Operators version 2.5.0* (<https://mpimet.mpg.de/cdo>)”.

The raw output from ICON-ESM-ER is stored well-structured and as large NetCDF files, enabling efficient scripting with processing tools like CDO CMOR without further auxiliary tools. In contrast, IFS-FESOM2 outputs data in a large amount of small files, and due to the complex directory and file structure, it is challenging to process the data without using the EERIE catalog.

One can open the EERIE catalog in Python as follows:

```
import intake

catalog="https://raw.githubusercontent.com/eerie-project/intake_c
atalogues/main/eerie.yaml"

eerie_cat=intake.open_catalog(catalog)
```

By using the [Cloudify tool](#) which was introduced by Wachsmann et al. (2025), IFS-FESOM2 output was processed with cdo cmor and using Zarr as the read interface.

What is Cloudify?

It is a tool designed to simplify the access and use of large climate simulation data, especially when it is stored in different formats or locations. Cloudify acts like a translator and organizer for this type of data, i.e. a native Zarr proxy. It builds on a flexible system called Xpublish, extending its functionality with additional features. This allows users to access the data through the Zarr over HTTP, as if it were already prepared for use in the cloud, even when it is not.

A custom Python script is used to launch a temporary Cloudify server on the Levante HPC system. This server makes accessible the target dataset (referenced via its Intake catalog URL) as Zarr, enabling on-the-fly adjustments such as variable renaming, level selection, time-shifting, and metadata updates, before CMORization. Then the modified dataset is processed directly in its intermediate, standardized form without generating large intermediate files. For instance, FESOM provides only daily surface ocean data; the background Python script calculates the monthly means before CMORizing them as monthly datasets.

As mentioned earlier, IFS-NEMO produces CMORized-like NetCDF files on a regular latitude-longitude grid for most of the variables. However, these NetCDF files do not fully

comply with CMOR standards. BSC has developed an in-house Python tool (which is not yet ready for publication) to apply a series of fixes to bring the data in line with CMOR standards. The tool uses a class-based, modular design, allowing it to function either as a data-quality checker or as a fixer. The series of fixes includes renaming files, adding metadata, and modifying variables and coordinates.

The Met Office system for CMORisation and publishing at CEDA JASMIN broadly follows the same processing as described above, but with their own software tools. The Climate Data Dissemination System (CDDS, <https://github.com/MetOffice/CDDS>) is a Python-based system that manages the reprocessing of HadGEM3 and UKESM1 climate model data into a standards compliant (CMOR) form suitable for publication and sharing. The primary driver behind CDDS was the CMIP6 project and CDDS was used, and is continuing to be used, to deliver a large amount of data to the [Centre for Environmental Data Archival \(CEDA\)](#) for publication to ESGF. It has been adapted to work with the Met Office EERIE model, which was not a registered, standard CMIP6 model, though currently it only works with atmospheric data (not with ocean and sea ice data). This processing also only works with native grid data, not the regrided data as described above. However, since the Met Office model atmosphere model uses a latitude-longitude grid anyway, this is not such a problem.

The workflow manager retrieves the model data from the Met Office data archive (MASS), processes it into CMOR-compliant form, and re-archives it to MASS. For EERIE, this data was then put onto the EERIE Group Workspace (GWS) at CEDA JASMIN, from where it was read into the CEDA tool for checking and publication to the CEDA Data Archive.

The CEDA process uses an EERIE-specific processing chain in the same ingestion and publication pipeline that is also used for Met Office CMIP data. A basic check on filenames and file sizes is performed, but the checks could later be expanded to include quality control using PrePARE if CMOR tables are provided. The files are ingested into the CEDA archive with a CMIP6-like directory structure, where the directory paths are based on facet values found in filenames and netCDF attributes. There is currently no step to publish the data to ESGF, but this could later be added if desired for new and existing data, subject to a suitable configuration being available.

2.3.1. Aggregation, Interpolation and Coordinates

Aggregation: CMOR output is expected to have consistent time intervals, for example, one file per year. To ensure uniformity across all datasets from a given model, the data were first merged into yearly files before applying CMOR. In our workflow, aggregation can be performed directly from a catalog input, where datasets are referenced through the EERIE intake catalog and combined virtually, or from concatenated input files, where the data are physically merged along the time dimension before processing. Eg:

- We choose annual time intervals for both ICON-ESM-ER and IFS-FESOM2.
- IFS-NEMO-ER: Outputs are written as 6-month time intervals following the model simulation chunks.
- IFS-FESOM2 provides only daily data for surface ocean: aggregated into monthly means

Coordinate Handling: Pre-processing involves specifying valid spatial and temporal coordinates. All datasets (except HadGEM3-GC5Es which are published on its native grid) prepared for publication are on a regular $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$ latitude–longitude grid, meaning that the regridding step described earlier has already been applied. At this stage, we verify that the spatial grid is correctly oriented. For example, the IFS-FESOM2 and IFS-NEMO re-gridded outputs have latitude values starting from 90° (North Pole) to -90° (South Pole), whereas CMOR standards require it to be from -90° to 90° . To meet this requirement, the latitude axis must be reversed so that the data align with the standard convention. Furthermore, for IFS-NEMO, the coordinates latitude and longitude are renamed to lat and lon, and their type is converted from float to double, in accordance with the CMOR table specifications.

The time axis often requires a dedicated focus because it is a common source of compliance errors. Here, the goal is to make time fully CF-compliant by setting the correct calendar, defining units in the form days since YYYY-MM-DD, and ensuring accurate time bounds. Adjusting or generating time bounds is essential for temporal accuracy. For example;

- The ICON-ESM-ER model output contains a systematic shift in the time axis. For instance, in the daily output, each time step is recorded at midnight (00:00:00 UTC),

but this timestamp actually represents data averaged over the previous day. For example, the file entry marked as 1950-01-02 00:00:00 corresponds to daily values for January 1st, not January 2nd. To correct this, we shift all time values backward by 43,200 seconds (12 hours), so that the timestamp indicates the mid-day of the correct day. After the correction, the same entry becomes 1950-01-01 12:00:00, properly representing the daily average for January 1st.

```
cdo -shifftime,-43200sec infile outfile
```

- Similarly, the IFS-FESOM output is written at midnight (e.g., 1950-01-01 00:00:00). CMOR applies a built-in adjustment that shifts timestamps to represent the midpoint of a day or month. For daily data, this can result in the time being shifted to the previous day (e.g., 1950-01-01 00:00:00 becomes 1949-12-31 12:00:00). To prevent this, the timestamps are adjusted to midday, by shifting them forward by 12 hours (e.g., 1950-01-01 00:00:00 becomes 1950-01-01 12:00:00), using the cdo:

```
cdo -shifftime,43200sec infile outfile
```

- For IFS-NEMO, the timestamps are shifted using the in-house fixer tool described earlier. The shift ensures that each timestamp is placed at the middle of the statistics window. In addition, time bounds are added and the variable type is converted from int64 to double.
- As mentioned earlier, IFS-FESOM2 monthly means were calculated from the daily output to get the monthly data. During this process, an issue was identified with the time bounds: they were incorrectly specified and filled with gaps. To resolve this, the time bounds were first removed from the original regridded files. CMOR then automatically generated and inserted the correct time bound values during processing.

2.3.2. Output

The standardized data to be published is stored fully compliant to the CMIP data standard defined in [CMIP6 model output requirements](#) document. The files are in the NetCDF4

classic format and conform to the CF (Climate and Forecast) Metadata Conventions making them suited for ESGF publication and long-term archival.

Files are organized in a standardized directory structure that encodes key metadata, including activity ID, institution, source model, experiment, variant, frequency, and variable name (figure 1). The output is typically compressed using zlib with fastest compression (deflate level of 1) to reduce storage requirements without compromising precision. Each file contains a consistent time span ensuring uniformity for the respected dataset. The root directory on levante for EERIE data is (`/work/bm1344/DKRZ/CMOR/EERIE/`).

Figure 1: Applied file name template for EERIE data.

2.4. Quality Control

Quality control (QC) ensures that all standardized datasets comply with the required data standard, and verifies the scientific validity of the data. At the file level, QC checks can confirm that datasets are complete, contain the correct number of time steps, and have no missing or corrupted records. Metadata verification ensures that all required global and variable attributes are present, such as variable names, units, standard names, coordinate definitions, and controlled vocabulary terms (e.g., activity ID, experiment ID, source ID). Grid checks confirm that the spatial domain is correct and oriented properly, and that coordinates follow the CMIP and CF conventions.

Scientific QC includes plotting variables to detect obvious inconsistencies, verifying physical ranges (e.g., large outliers), and ensuring no unrealistic temporal or spatial jumps occur. We also check whether bounds are correct, time steps are regular, and that the dataset covers the expected period without gaps or overlaps.

At DKRZ, the in-house [Quality Control Tool](#) has been applied to assure high data quality. This tool systematically checks NetCDF files against the EERIE requirements, highlighting deviations such as missing/incorrect attributes, incorrect controlled vocabulary terms, incorrect file names or incompatible coordinate definitions. Any issues identified during QC are addressed before final publication. An [example QC check](#) for EERIE ICON-ESM-ER historical dataset is shown in the figure 2.

Load QC Results From Repository:

2025-07-11 06:53: EERIE_ICON-ESM-ER_hist-1950_r1 (.work.bm1344.DKRZ.CM ▾)

Or Select a Local QC Summary File:

Choose File no file selected

Quality Control Summary

QC Results for 'EERIE_ICON-ESM-ER_hist-1950_r1 (.work.bm1344.DKRZ.CMOR.EERIE.HighResMIP.MPI-M.ICON-ESM-ER.hist-1950.r1i1p1f1.*)' (from: 2025-07-11 06:53)

IOOS Compliance Checker (5.3.1.dev13+g1f63a76) - CF-Conventions cf:1.7, MIP mip:0.2.1.dev2+g9b9e5ab

-- checked 109 datasets & 7087 files --

Expand/Collapse Runtime Errors Expand/Collapse Failed Checks

▼ Runtime Errors

▼ [MIP] check_variable_definition

▶ Exception: too many indices for array: array is 0-dimensional, but 1 were indexed at /work/bb1364/dkrz/cc-plugin-cc6/cc_plugin_cc6/base.py:1265 in function/method 'check_variable_definition'. Potentially affected variables: siconc.

Figure 2: Output from QA tool.

For IFS-NEMO, the in-house fixer tool can also be used as a quality control checker. Additionally, we use standard CMOR-CF compliance checks and as a final test we run an [ESMValTool](#) recipe on the data. This also allows for a comparison with the other EERIE models to verify that the variables follow the same standards.

3. Publication

3.1. ESGF and CEDA Data Archive

All HighResMIP-style simulations are published at the Earth System Grid Federation (ESGF) under the project ID *EERIE* (available at [ESGF MetaGrid](#)). The CMIP6-style simulations produced by the Met Office are made available at the Centre for Environmental Data Analysis (CEDA) archive (<https://archive.ceda.ac.uk/>). The published total number of variables are shown in Table 3 and 4.

For EERIE, a project-specific entry was created in the ESGF Metagrid frontend, and corresponding configuration files for the ESGF publisher were generated. During publication, the publisher extracts all relevant metadata from the NetCDF file headers and contents to complete the ESGF search index. Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) for each dataset are automatically generated and also the `tracking_ids` in the files are registered with the global Handle System, ensuring traceability and long-term reference. The published datasets are made available through HTTP download endpoints, enabling global access via the ESGF infrastructure.

Model	1950-control	1950-hist	Highres-future-ssp245
ICON-ESM-ER	112	122	122
IFS-FESOM2	-	92	92
IFS-NEMO-EERIE			

Table 3: Published number of variables in ESGF

Model	PiControl (years)	historical (1850-2014)	Scenario (2015-2100)
HadGEM3-GC5E-HH	-	18	-

Model	PiControl (years)	historical (1850-2014)	Scenario (2015-2100)
HadGEM3-GC5E-LL	-	18	-
HadGEM3-GC5E-MM	-	18	-

Table 4: Published variables in CEDA Data Archive.

Note: At the time of submitting this document, the publication of IFS-NEMO-EERIE on ESGF was still blocked at the PID generation due to some unprecedented machine technical difficulties. It might take only a few more days to generate them and they can be provided on demand later on, or accessible directly on the ESGF, but the data will be available with the other models by the end of September.

3.2. User Guidance

Here we present how to navigate and download the EERIE data from the ESGF. The EERIE data is public and can be downloaded on [Metagrid DKRZ node](#) (for both ICON-ESM-ER, IFS-FESOM2-SR, and IFS-NEMO-EERIE data) without creating an account or login. All the ESGF nodes can be found at: <https://esgf.github.io/nodes.html>.

1. Search and Discover Data

Use the ESGF web portal to perform free-text searches. You can filter by project, model, variable, time period, or institution. E.g:

Figure 3: ESGF interface, search by project ID.

Figure 4: ESGF interface, overview of the datasets.

Figure 5: ESGF interface, overview of the files.

Figure 5 shows how to navigate to get the dropdown menu for available files and file description or to get the metadata by clicking the red-circled metadata entry.

2. Choose Download Method

Once you find relevant data, you can download it via HTTP or wget scripts generated directly from the portal (Figure 5 green circle)

3. Programmatic Access

Tools like [intake-esgf](#) (Python) and [pyesgf](#) enable scripting for searches and downloads, useful for automated workflows.

For Met Office data on the CEDA data archive, this is available from:

<https://data.ceda.ac.uk/badc/cmip6/data/EERIE>

CEDA provides [user guidance](#) containing all the necessary information. Figures 6 and 7 below illustrate how to access the EERIE data and the available download options.

Figure 6: CEDA Archive interface, search by project ID and resolutions.

Figure 7: CEDA Archive data download, example variable precipitation

Annexes

PiDs for ICON hist-1950 dataset (EERIE.HighResMIPMPI-M.ICON-ESM-ER.hist-1950.r1i1p1f1.)	
day.hursmin.gr.v20240618	hdl:21.14102/304c42b2-723b-342b-8c60-e00c5c87b17d
day.tasmax.gr.v20240618	hdl:21.14102/7eebe541-1907-3dc0-8fd0-0a4a97f7c680
Omon.mlotstsq.gr.v20240618	hdl:21.14102/dc71a322-5e4d-3256-9395-d0563f47f53d
SImon.siconc.gr.v20240618	hdl:21.14102/7a2b3b93-474a-39dc-9792-bd17400035a1
Amon.cli.gr.v20240618	hdl:21.14102/a2218f98-88d5-3d24-b559-fa3de94f739a
HRday.ua19.gr.v20240618	hdl:21.14102/3c838080-dd31-35a9-9872-233d5b778c9c
SImon.siu.gr.v20240618	hdl:21.14102/7430527b-13a0-31f8-8fef-097b9f2f59af
day.tasmin.gr.v20240618	hdl:21.14102/52dd50b6-c8c3-302d-9f2d-114317b4b94b
Omon.mlotst.gr.v20240618	hdl:21.14102/b718f00d-0083-3909-b0e7-5aca67732151
Amon.psl.gr.v20240618	hdl:21.14102/d5c67925-190b-338d-81fb-91dfa864b28a
Amon.tauu.gr.v20240618	hdl:21.14102/de87330d-d475-3769-8490-c9e08ad8b0b2
Amon.rsuscs.gr.v20240618	hdl:21.14102/9611b240-7a64-3e28-95bf-b2320504fda9
SIday.siconc.gr.v20240618	hdl:21.14102/3f51a37f-7baa-324f-9921-f1979d70b9f2
Amon.zg.gr.v20240618	hdl:21.14102/430331ff-0838-3b85-b0cf-52ed44674085
Oday.tos.gr.v20240618	hdl:21.14102/f49c7e84-2021-33c0-89de-86e753de757e
Amon.hur.gr.v20240618	hdl:21.14102/de4ca693-b98f-3059-8312-685004834681
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SImon.sithick.gr.v20240618	hdl:21.14102/abd87808-0dd6-3765-82ab-56f7f6d7996d
day.hursmax.gr.v20240618	hdl:21.14102/4bde4edc-5960-3f9d-8b9c-3c8770f5dcce
Amon.rsus.gr.v20240618	hdl:21.14102/c49cff9d-2023-3298-9167-18d126b0a611
Amon.tas.gr.v20240618	hdl:21.14102/a967675a-205c-3945-b069-190f5fd700cd

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HRday.hus19.gr.v20240618	hdl:21.14102/8c2f8271-4009-38af-843a-3ddcaad56905
HR0day.tauuo.gr.v20240618	hdl:21.14102/0c856402-e09a-38fe-8f4a-fc51a3bed9ed
HR0day.uos.gr.v20240618	hdl:21.14102/a1f1921a-c975-3409-9022-1143bdf941e3
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HR0day.tauvo.gr.v20240618	hdl:21.14102/334fb3ef-6101-3901-8219-4feef9ee811b
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HR0day.vos.gr.v20240618	hdl:21.14102/4f704f1c-e8ae-3e71-99cc-d9edb43f74f4
HR0day.rsntds.gr.v20240618	hdl:21.14102/92a710ec-8848-36d6-a2bb-ce4831529e22
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Omon.tos.gr.v20240618	hdl:21.14102/aeccda38-542b-3b17-ac83-a1d606260b31
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Amon.tauv.gr.v20240618	hdl:21.14102/e1e6eb00-87a5-3695-9f1f-c5bd2eb690a7
day.sfcWind.gr.v20240618	hdl:21.14102/424acb8b-ba97-3beb-9f61-2b16a0213ce6
day.hurs.gr.v20240618	hdl:21.14102/4da0e127-a8eb-3bd6-b612-454c25a16413
day.uas.gr.v20240618	hdl:21.14102/f8e13812-0621-39ef-bcd9-b7a4e1042d43
Omon.pso.gr.v20240618	hdl:21.14102/da859830-33f1-3900-bf6b-73bb756afb34

.HROmon.wo.gr.v20240618	hdl:21.14102/95fbcca4-d37f-31b4-8139-8dcdcc07f0b2
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HRday.ta19.gr.v20240618	hdl:21.14102/ab99cd8b-ec9d-37c0-afc5-1c7b082ec5de
HRday.va19.gr.v20240618	hdl:21.14102/6157c785-5739-35d1-87f9-ca726c685392
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PiDs for ICON eerie-control-1950 dataset (EERIE.EERIE.MPI-M.ICON-ESM-ER.eerie-control-1950.r1i1p1f1.)	
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Amon.rsus.gr.v20240618	hdl:21.14102/d0fb20a9-c3e9-32a1-8f04-8344025a8c3c
Amon.rlus.gr.v20240618	hdl:21.14102/c06fb9e6-3197-3fd2-9e09-5c9f39ba868d
Amon.rsdscs.gr.v20240618	hdl:21.14102/99d3388c-2409-331d-94a5-0b4287ce1f72
Amon.rsdt.gr.v20240618	hdl:21.14102/e1fd3a34-09d6-3531-aeed-1306ee172713
Amon.rlut.gr.v20240618	hdl:21.14102/cabd4400-230b-334d-aeb6-34d093100b7c
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HRday.hus19.gr.v20240618	hdl:21.14102/db448bd6-ed60-370f-bc73-a828d8a5d766
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HROday.wo.gr.v20240618	hdl:21.14102/803f3cc0-79d3-3d04-a13b-c17e09b8736c
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HROmon.wo.gr.v20240618	hdl:21.14102/31e87424-961b-3ef4-9666-ba431c33efe2
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Amon.uas.gr.v20240618	hdl:21.14102/a5996569-44f9-39e9-ac6e-440e774f6234
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Amon.tas.gr.v20240618	hdl:21.14102/ed0ac93c-07b4-3ccc-8f21-4991825274c3
Amon.tauu.gr.v20240618	hdl:21.14102/3f9b9c13-78e1-3514-a808-41793af4d6af
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Slmon.sithick.gr.v20240618	hdl:21.14102/fbc02870-f8d2-39ba-948d-b9e9cf4ddbe0
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Amon.hfls.gr.v20240618	hdl:21.14102/3d81efc2-ddb1-3441-aad2-caf4d4dbec8b
Amon.pr.gr.v20240618	hdl:21.14102/0c4e9a44-76ad-3277-8636-0caa22e54f45
Amon.ps.gr.v20240618	hdl:21.14102/4ec71374-3398-3f95-98d1-92d01ee959b7
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PiDs for ICON future-ssp245 datasets

(EERIE.HighResMIP.MPI-M.ICON-ESM-ER.highres-future-ssp245.r1i1p1f1)

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PiDs for IFS-FESOM2 hist-1950 datasets

(EERIE.HighResMIP.AWI.IFS-FESOM2-SR.hist-1950.r1i1p1f1)

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**UK Research
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